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Protein Engineering Based Catalytic Cite Analysis of NAD⁺ Dependent Mutant *Ceriporiopsis subvermispota* Format Dehydrogenase Enzyme

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The understanding of the mechanism of enzymatic recovery of NADH is of biological and of considerable biotechnological interest, since the essential, but expensive, cofactor NADH is exhausted in asymmetric hydrogenation processes, but can be recovered by NAD⁺-dependent format dehydrogenase (FDH). In this research we have used *Ceriporiopsis subvermispota* Formate dehydrogenase (CsFDH) due to its very low enzymatic activity compared to other FDH enzymes. Two amino acid positions which are 312. and 313. have been decided due to their unsimilarities to the other well-known FDH enzymes. The study progressed rational design process on 312. and 313. position of CsFDH by mutating from asparagine to phenylalanine and valine to proline, respectively. The roles of these positions in the reaction mechanism have been investigated due to their effects on the enzyme activity. CsFDH Val313Pro has shown relatively high activity on the reaction, while CsFDH Asn312Phe has shown no significant change on the activity. This study important for analysis of the catalytic region that provides FDH production and gives information for determination of the importance of enzyme production and provide information for similar scientific studies.

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